

A Note on Generalized BPS Monopoles via Spatial Deformation Field

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In this note, we show that BPS magnetic monopoles can be generalized in a spatially deformed metric, where the metric $g_{\mu\nu}$ is postulated as a dependent variable of a scalar field σ and taking the form $g_{00} = 1, g_{0i} = 0, g_{ij} = e^{2\sigma} \eta_{ij}$ in certain coordinate systems. We demonstrate that the action can be exactly rewritten as an integral of a sum of σ -weighted quadratic terms and a boundary term by completing the squares. This structure ensures that the generalized BPS equations involving σ -field and the static condition lead to a stationary point of the action, and σ -field turns out to be a moduli field-like variational variable. Furthermore, we can introduce an additional action S_σ governing the σ -field while preserving the generalized BPS structure. The resulting energy E_σ supplements the topological bound.

I. INTRODUCTION

The 't Hooft-Polyakov magnetic monopole[1] in non-Abelian gauge-Higgs theories plays a crucial role in understanding the non-perturbative regime. In particular, the BPS monopole[2], which corresponds to the zero-potential limit, admits highly elegant exact solutions via Bogomol'nyi's method. However, the presence of the potential breaks this BPS structure, restricting the theory to rigid exact solutions and a fixed mass lower bound. In this note, we postulate that the metric $g_{\mu\nu}$ is a dependent variable of a scalar field σ and taking the form $g_{00} = 1, g_{0i} = 0, g_{ij} = e^{2\sigma} \eta_{ij} = -e^{2\sigma} \delta_{ij}$ in certain coordinate systems. Under this postulation, we demonstrate that the BPS monopole can be generalized. Because the σ -field behaves as a modulus field with respect to the monopole action S_M . The hedgehog radial equations derived from the generalized BPS equations admit a rich class of exact solutions via the function σ . Furthermore, we consider adding the action S_σ describing the dynamics of σ to S_M and show that the BPS structure is preserved.

II. FORMULATION

Let us consider the BPS-limit SO(3) Yang-Mills-Higgs system defined on a spacetime characterized by a scalar field σ . We postulate that the metric $g_{\mu\nu}$ depends on σ and takes the form $g_{00} = 1, g_{0i} = 0, g_{ij} = e^{2\sigma} \eta_{ij} = -e^{2\sigma} \delta_{ij}$ in certain coordinate systems.

Note: Our focus is not on Einstein gravity, and thus the dynamical variable is the σ , not $g_{\mu\nu}$ as stated earlier.

The action functional is generally defined as

$$S_M = \int \sqrt{-g} \left[-\frac{1}{4} g^{\mu\lambda} g^{\nu\rho} F_{\mu\nu}^a F_{\lambda\rho}^a + \frac{1}{2} g^{\mu\nu} D_\mu \phi^a D_\nu \phi^a \right] d^4x \quad (1)$$

Substituting the metric defined above, we obtain

$$S_M = \int e^{3\sigma} \left[\frac{e^{-2\sigma}}{2} (F_{0i}^a)^2 - \frac{e^{-4\sigma}}{4} (F_{ij}^a)^2 + \frac{1}{2} (D_0 \phi^a)^2 - \frac{e^{-2\sigma}}{2} (D_i \phi^a)^2 \right] d^4x \quad (2)$$

The integrand becomes a sum of squares weighted by the exponential of σ . By absorbing the square root of

this weight into each squared term and defining B_i^a as $B_i^a = \frac{1}{2} \epsilon_{ijk} F_{ij}^a$, the action can be expressed as

$$S_M = \int \left[\frac{1}{2} (e^{\frac{\sigma}{2}} F_{0i}^a)^2 + \frac{1}{2} (e^{\frac{3\sigma}{2}} D_0 \phi^a)^2 - \frac{1}{2} (e^{\frac{-\sigma}{2}} B_i^a)^2 - \frac{1}{2} (e^{\frac{\sigma}{2}} D_i \phi^a)^2 \right] d^4x \quad (3)$$

Completing the square for the terms B_i^a and $D_i \phi^a$, we can extract the standard BPS boundary term $B_i^a D_i \phi^a$ since the factors $e^{-\frac{\sigma}{2}}$ and $e^{\frac{\sigma}{2}}$ cancel each other, and rewrite the action as

$$S_M = \int \left[\frac{1}{2} (e^{\frac{\sigma}{2}} F_{0i}^a)^2 + \frac{1}{2} (e^{\frac{3\sigma}{2}} D_0 \phi^a)^2 - \frac{1}{2} (e^{\frac{-\sigma}{2}} B_i^a \mp e^{\frac{\sigma}{2}} D_i \phi^a)^2 \mp B_i^a D_i \phi^a \right] d^4x \quad (4)$$

Using $D_i B_i^a = 0$ and defining $\mathcal{X}_i^a, \mathcal{Y}^a, \mathcal{Z}_i^a$ as

$$\mathcal{X}_i^a = e^{\frac{\sigma}{2}} F_{0i}^a, \mathcal{Y}^a = e^{\frac{3\sigma}{2}} D_0 \phi^a, \mathcal{Z}_i^a = e^{\frac{-\sigma}{2}} B_i^a \mp e^{\frac{\sigma}{2}} D_i \phi^a \quad (5)$$

we can rewrite the action S_M as

$$S_M = \int \left[\frac{1}{2} (\mathcal{X}_i^a)^2 + \frac{1}{2} (\mathcal{Y}^a)^2 - \frac{1}{2} (\mathcal{Z}_i^a)^2 \right] d^4x \mp \int dt \oint_{S_\infty^2} B_i^a \phi^a dS_i \quad (6)$$

Under the static conditions $\partial_0 = 0, A_0^a = 0$ and the generalized BPS conditions $B_i^a \mp e^\sigma D_i \phi^a = 0$, we find that $\mathcal{X}_i^a = 0, \mathcal{Y}^a = 0, \mathcal{Z}_i^a = 0$.

The above structure and the vanishing of the variation of boundary integral term due to the fixed boundary conditions immediately imply that the total action variation vanishes :

$$\delta S_M = \int [\mathcal{X}_i^a \delta \mathcal{X}_i^a + \mathcal{Y}^a \delta \mathcal{Y}^a - \mathcal{Z}_i^a \delta \mathcal{Z}_i^a] d^4x = 0 \quad (7)$$

Therefore, for configurations satisfying the generalized BPS conditions and static conditions, the variation of the action S_M with respect to all dynamical variables $[A_\mu^a, \phi^a, \sigma]$ vanishes.

The generalized BPS condition $B_i^a = \pm e^\sigma D_i \phi^a$ can

be rewritten using the rescaled field φ^a ($\phi^a = \varphi^a e^{-\sigma}$) and modified covariant derivative $\mathcal{D}_i = D_i - \partial_i \sigma$ as

$$B_i^a = \pm \mathcal{D}_i \varphi^a = \pm (D_i \varphi^a - \varphi^a \partial_i \sigma) \quad (8)$$

The term $-\partial_i \sigma$ acts as an effective connection. The σ -field behaves as a moduli-like field; despite being a dynamical variable, we retain the freedom to prescribe it as an arbitrary function.

III. RADIAL EQUATIONS

We have obtained the generalized BPS equations in Eq.(8). To obtain radial equations, we employ the hedgehog ansatz for the gauge field A_i^a and the Higgs field φ^a as follows

$$\varphi^a(r) = \frac{x^a}{er} H(r), A_i^a = \epsilon_{aij} \frac{x^j}{er^2} (1 - K(r)), \sigma = \sigma(r) \quad (9)$$

By applying the hedgehog to the generalized BPS equations, $B_i^a = \pm \mathcal{D}_i \varphi^a$, the effective connection term $\mp \varphi^a \partial_i \sigma$ is identified as the deviation from the standard BPS equations: $B_i^a \mp D_i \varphi^a = \mp \varphi^a \partial_i \sigma$.

The radial equations are as follows:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{dK}{dr} = \mp KH \\ \frac{dH}{dr} = \frac{d\sigma}{dr} H \pm \frac{1 - K^2}{r^2} \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

From the topological boundary condition $|\phi^a| \rightarrow \text{const.}$ as $r \rightarrow \infty$, we choose $K(r) \rightarrow 0$ and $H(r) \rightarrow \text{const.}$, and $\sigma \rightarrow 0$ as $r \rightarrow \infty$. For regularity at the origin, we set $K(0) = 1$ and $H(0) = 0$.

The profile functions $K(r)$ and $H(r)$ constitute a rich class of exact solutions via the moduli-like field σ . In other words, $K(r)$ and $H(r)$ can be defined as the special functions functionally parameterized by σ .

IV. MASSIVE MONOPOLE VIA THE σ -SECTOR

Up to this point, the fact that σ acts as a moduli-like field for S_M has allowed us to treat it as an arbitrary function in the equations.

In this section, we show that we can add the term S_σ describing the dynamics of σ to the monopole action S_M while preserving the generalized BPS structure.

We define the total action $S = S_M [A_\mu^a, \phi^a, \sigma] + S_\sigma [\sigma]$. The variational principle of the total action S is given by

$$\delta S = \delta S_M + \delta S_\sigma = 0 \quad (11)$$

Under the static conditions and the generalized BPS conditions, as demonstrated earlier, the variation of the

monopole sector vanishes, $\delta S_M = 0$, with respect to all dynamical variables $[A_\mu^a, \phi^a, \sigma]$.

Consequently, since S_σ is a functional solely of σ , the variational principle $\delta S = 0$ reduces to the static set of

$$\begin{cases} B_i^a = \pm \mathcal{D}_i \varphi^a \\ \frac{\delta S_\sigma}{\delta \sigma} = 0 \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

In other words, the monopole sector exerts no back-reaction on the dynamics of σ . This implies that the two sectors are unidirectionally (or one-way) decoupled; one can first determine σ by solving the equation of motion $\frac{\delta S_\sigma}{\delta \sigma} = 0$, and subsequently substitute this solution into the generalized BPS equations to obtain the monopole field configuration.

Here, if the action of σ field S_σ yields a positive-defined energy $E_\sigma \geq 0$ and supports stable configurations (e.g. by including higher-order kinetic terms like the Skyrme term and a suitable potential), the total energy of the system M becomes

$$M = |Q_M| + E_\sigma \quad (13)$$

Therefore, σ field energy E_σ effectively elevates the topological lower bound. Equivalently, in this case, this system constitutes a composite (or dual) soliton of the monopole and the σ -field.

In an inverse-problem context, we also can reconstruct σ and S_σ from the prescribed profile function $K(r)$ and $H(r)$. From Eq.(10), the equation for σ is derived as

$$\frac{d\sigma(r)}{dr} = \frac{d}{dr} \log H(r) \pm \frac{K(r)^2 - 1}{r^2 H(r)} \quad (14)$$

Since Eq.(12) shows that the σ -field decouples from the monopole fields, one can first determine σ from Eq.(14) for a given set of $K(r)$ and $H(r)$. The apparent singularity in Eq.(14) vanishes due to the regularity of $K(r)$ and $H(r)$ combined with the algebraic constraint at the origin imposed by $\frac{dK}{dr} = \mp KH$, thereby guaranteeing that $\sigma(r)$ is regular at the origin. We can then construct the σ -field action S_σ supporting this σ as an solution to $\frac{\delta S_\sigma}{\delta \sigma} = 0$.

V. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, we have demonstrated that the BPS monopole is generalized by the spatial deformation field σ , allowing for a rich class of structures. Remarkably, even when the spatial components of the metric are deformed by the σ -field, the topological term remains invariant and the BPS structure is preserved. While we expect the σ -field to originate from a more general framework such as Weyl theory or scalar-tensor gravity, and S_σ to be interpreted as the counterpart to the Higgs potential, we defer these investigations to future work.

[1] G.'t Hooft, Nucl. Phys. B. **79**, 276(1974);
A. M. Polyakov, JETP Lett. **20**, 194(1974).

[2] M. K. Prasad and C. M. Sommerfield, PRL. **35**, 760(1975);
E. B. Bogomol'nyi, Sov. J. Nucl. Phys. **24**, 499(1976).